

I FAIR Program: Data Management Plan Guidelines

V4

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Document Versioning

Revision	Author/s	Main changes
v1 19 May 2021	CRS4	First version
v1.1 2 July 2021	CRS4	First version, with integration from SR
v2 5 December 2023	CRS4	Minor revisions
v3 28 December 2023	CRS4	Minor revisions
v4 10 April 2026	CRS4/SR	Minor revisions and updates

1. Document scope and objectives

This document has been created by CRS4 within the technical support activities of the I FAIR Program¹, aiming to qualify the provision of clinical research services in Sardinia through the introduction of FAIR data principles² (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable*).

The Program aims to spread the culture of quality and re-use for data associated with independent clinical study, in a path towards the FAIRification of data collected in the regional clinical research and foresees:

- the creation of a tool allowing to know the types of data associated with studies in Sardinia and collect them in a FAIR metadata registry (the FAIR Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia-R3B³);
- the improvement of the acquisition, management and use of the data collected during a study, through:
 - financial support to a set of selected studies, providing them with a budget dedicated to the FAIRification activities;
 - advice on bioethics, medical statistics, patient expert and technological training interventions supporting the Principal Investigator (PI) who will take care of the collected data lifecycle and will draw up the Data Management Plan (DMP) with the Data Steward (DS) and the study staff.

During the first technical seminar, DSs and studies' staff have been trained on what the FAIR guiding principles are, their objective and how to apply them. In particular, subjects of the training

¹ Programma IFAIR di Sardegna Ricerche - <https://www.sardegna-ricerche.it/index.php?xsl=370&s=439313&v=2&c=6072&nc=1&sc=>

² Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ The Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia - R3B - www.ifair.crs4.it

have been the creation of a DMP and the introduction of how to express univocally the meaning of data and metadata, associating them to the main ontologies.

A **Data Management Plan** is:

- a document accompanying the research work and describing the data collected, processed and generated, where they are stored, what licences and restrictions are attached to them, who has the right to use them (**DATA**);
- a reference for dealing with data responsibly and making them FAIR (**MANAGEMENT**);
- a schedule for the collection, preservation and re-use of data and metadata, from the beginning of the activity (**PLAN**).

The DMP is a **living document** that can be drafted in various versions depending on the progress of the research.

The approach followed in the I FAIR Program for the technical support to create and update a DMP leaves the DS free of using the preferred tools/wizards for its creation (some of them are cited in the References section), but highlighting the main dimensions of the contents, including a set of mandatory information that has to be included in the DMP.

The objectives of this document are:

- to **support the DS in the understanding of the main dimension of a DMP**, selected from a comparison of the structures of DMPs present at the time of writing in the research community;
- to **guide** the DS in the creation and update of the DMP.

The DSs are free to organise the elements in their DMPs, but it is **required to include all the elements marked as “mandatory”** in the sections of this guide.

Finally, in order to improve the clarity and readability of the DMP, it is suggested that it should not be set up in the form of question-answers, as is the case with some outputs of the wizards available on the web, but organised in sections for which the title is the question, while the content is the answer of the document generated automatically by the wizards.

2. Main dimensions

2.1 Approach

Several DMP templates have been analysed and compared to find commonalities and specificities between the contents, also integrating what is considered useful according to direct experience. This document contains a summary about the findings, by giving an overview of the common sections and content and including also some guiding information from the templates. For each section, a brief explanation (i.e., “Rationale”) and a list of the most common aspects are given; in addition, references to external tools or training resources (“Guidance”) and advice are given, when possible, while the required elements are grouped in the “Mandatory Elements” section. Source templates are always indicated in the text with acronyms within square brackets and listed in the References.

The main sections to be included in the DMP, described in detail in the next paragraphs, are:

- General information;
- Data management:
 - Collection and generation;
 - Documentation and metadata;
 - Shareability, publication and re-use;
 - FAIRness;
- Resources;
- Security, storage and backup;
- Ethical, legal, administrative and privacy aspects.

Always remind that **what is in DMP must be consistent and compliant with what has been included in the study protocol and in the documents approved by the Ethical Review Board.**

There are several web tools available to create a DMP, such as Data Stewardship Wizard [<https://ds-wizard.org/>] and DMP Tool [<https://dmptool.org/>], which automatically generate the document based on existent or custom templates (see here for some examples of publicly shared plans https://dmptool.org/public_plans)

2.2 General information

Rationale. To give an overview of the project in terms of goals, funding, duration and involved staff.

Aspects to be considered

Title and abstract of the project; project acronym; objectives; partners; Principal Investigator/Project Manager; Data Steward; project status; duration or start/end of project; internal/external policies or guidelines; DMP version/date; contact person for data management and access **[UniBi], [SRC], [SNSF]**.

Mandatory Elements

Title and abstract of the project; project acronym; objectives; partners; Principal Investigator; Data Steward duration or start/end of project, if available; internal/external policies or guidelines; DMP version/date.

2.3 Data management

Rationale. To provide a summary of all the aspects related to the data management within the project, taking into account different aspects such as purpose of the data collection/generation, types and formats, possible re-use of existing data (if any), data origin, expected size of the data, documentation and metadata, data quality policies, data publication and distribution.

This dimension is further divided into the following sections: “Collection and generation”, “Documentation and metadata”, “Shareability, publication and re-use” and “FAIRness”.

2.3.1 Collection and generation

Rationale: To describe briefly the data that will be collected, observed or generated and which methods will be used, giving also justification to the choices made. Any existing data that can and/or will be (re)used should be mentioned and described, also in relation to those that will be generated in addition. Reasons for which the re-use of any existing data has been discarded should be reported too. Describe how consistency and data quality will be documented and controlled.

Aspects to be considered

Purpose of the data collection; data utility⁴; description of data, specifically collected or pre-existing the project, in-house or third parties' data (availability, integration with generated data, sources, type, format, policies, etc.); collected/generated data kinds, types (spreadsheets, databases, textual files, images, mixed, etc.), formats (e.g., pdf, xls, doc, txt, rdf) and the expected volume (if known); needs for special software solutions; data collection/generation methods (survey, clinical measurements, interviews, genotyping, patient records, etc.); data process methods; data provenance; relevant community standards and controlled vocabularies; quality assurance procedures (e.g., calibration processes, repeated measurements, data entry validation, data peer review, etc.); data handling (naming conventions, folder structures, collaborative work, data transfer, etc.); data versioning [H2020],[HE], [SNSF], [DCC], [NSF], [UniBi], [HRB], [NWO].

Guidance

Give preference to open and standard formats as they facilitate sharing and long-term re-use of data. Several repositories provide lists of such 'preferred formats' (see e.g. [DANS File Formats](#) and [4TU.ResearchData Preferred Formats](#))[NWO].

Mandatory Elements

Purpose of the data collection; description of data, specifically collected or pre-existing the project, in-house or third parties' data (availability, integration with generated data, sources, type, format, policies, etc.); collected/generated data kinds, types (spreadsheets, databases, textual files, images, mixed, etc.), formats (e.g., pdf, xls, doc, txt, rdf); needs for special software solutions; data collection/generation methods (survey, clinical measurements, interviews, genotyping, patient records, etc.); data process methods; relevant community standards and controlled vocabularies; data handling (naming conventions, folder structures, collaborative work, data transfer, etc.); data versioning.

2.3.2 Documentation and metadata

Rationale. To describe all types of documentation (README files, metadata, etc.) that will be provided to support data understanding and re-use. Metadata should at least include basic details allowing other users (computer or human) to find the data (minimally: the file name, a persistent identifier, collection date, access conditions, etc.). Furthermore, the documentation

⁴ 'Data utility' means "To whom might it be useful"

may include details on: the methodology used, the performed processing and analytical steps, variable definitions, references to vocabularies used, as well as units of measurement, possibly following existing community standards and guidelines. This section should explain how this information will be prepared and shared [SNSF].

Aspects to be considered

Documentation content and purpose (data description, definitions of variables, units of measurement, contextual information, procedures, processing, data quality measures, etc.); documentation availability (where recorded and how is accessible) and formats (e.g., a 'readme' text file, file headers, code books, lab notebook, etc.); metadata (e.g., purpose, types, formats and standard scheme, standards, machine-readability, generation or collection); data searchability (unique and persistent identifiers, workflows for data identification, etc.); software requirements and necessary knowledge for (meta)data processing [SNSF], [DCC], [NSF], [UniBi], [HRB], [NWO], [SRC].

Guidance

- Where these are in place, researchers are advised to use community metadata standards. The Research Data Alliance maintains a [Directory of Metadata Standards](#) [NWO].
- Note the standards to be used for data and metadata format and content (where existing standards are absent or deemed inadequate, this should be documented along with any proposed solutions or remedies) [NSF].

Mandatory Elements

Documentation content and purpose (data description, definitions of variables, units of measurement, contextual information, procedures, processing, data quality measures, etc.); documentation availability (where recorded and how is accessible) and formats (e.g., a 'readme' text file, file headers, code books, lab notebook, etc.); software requirements and necessary knowledge for (meta)data processing.

2.3.3 Shareability, publication and re-use

Rationale. This paragraph should describe the main aspects of data sharing, including methods, repositories, how the re-use is regulated, timing for release and restrictions [SNSF].

Aspects to be considered

Data repositories (e.g., trustworthy data repository, indexed in a catalogue, direct handling of data requests, proprietary/not-commercial, generic/domain-specific platforms, FAIR compliance); data discoverability; sharing conditions and policies (data selection, licenses, Data Access Committee, chargeable access, timing of data release, reason for delay if applicable, justification in case of no shareability, acknowledgement for data re-use, access procedures) and limitations motivations (legal, ethical, copyright, confidentiality or other clauses); obligation for data release (if existing); long-term preservation plan (long-term value data selection, deposit, data that needs to be retained or destroyed for contractual/regulatory reasons, archives, resources, curation, etc.); interoperability aspects (e.g., special software or tool needed for data interpretation and re-use like specific scripts, codes or algorithms developed during the project);

potential reasons (e.g., study validation, dissemination, new research, etc.) and foreseeable users for data sharing [SNSF], [DCC], [UniBi], [SRC], [NSF], [HRB], [NWO].

Guidance

- Consider using a generic FAIR-compliant platform (see the [example](#)) for data deposit if there are no suitable specific repositories for the considered research field [SNSF];
- [Repository Finder](#) can help to find an appropriate repository to deposit research data; data licenses can be expressed through the commonly used Creative Commons licenses, and a [wizard](#) can help to choose the correct one. Check also the [Five Recommendations for FAIR Software](#). [NWO].

Mandatory Elements

Sharing conditions and policies (data selection, licenses, Data Access Committee, chargeable access, timing of data release, reason for delay if applicable, justification in case of no shareability, acknowledgement for data re-use, access procedures) and limitations motivations (legal, ethical, copyright, confidentiality or other clauses); long-term preservation plan (long-term value data selection, deposit, data that needs to be retained or destroyed for contractual/regulatory reasons, archives, resources, curation, etc.); interoperability aspects (e.g., special software or tool needed for data interpretation and re-use like specific scripts, codes or algorithms developed during the project).

Preparing this section also consider what will be included in the study protocol and in the documents to send⁵⁶.

2.3.4 FAIRness

This section is only contained in the European Commission's DMP templates (i.e., **Horizon2020** and its successor **Horizon Europe**), which is inspired by the FAIR culture and strongly promotes the adoption and use of the Guiding Principles. Given the general applicability and importance of the concepts expressed by the Principles, it is interesting to note that many of the contents expressed here are also part of the other templates and simply distributed across more sections and without a precise reference to the four FAIR dimensions. However, among all, also the **SNSF** DMP template recalls the FAIR principles by stating explicitly the correspondence between each section and one or more of them.

Even if this section's content can be included in other sections, some of the things listed here represent a step forward in the application of the open science philosophy (e.g., open source code, usage of open repositories for data deposition, boost of machine-readability, etc.) and therefore are an undoubted added value to the project if considered carefully.

⁶ Example: "I dati riferiti ai singoli pazienti rimarranno nella disponibilità dello Sperimentatore che li trasmetterà, qualora richiesti, in forma rigorosamente anonimizzata o pseudononimizzata ad altri Sperimentatori che hanno accesso alla piattaforma solamente dopo l'autorizzazione da parte di un Comitato Etico e/o di un Comitato Tecnico-Scientifico Indipendente. [...] Qualora richiesti da altri sperimentatori, i dati saranno trasmessi dallo sperimentatore in forma aggregata ed anonimizzata: lo sperimentatore non trasferirà quindi i dati individuali (riferiti al singolo paziente) ma quelli riferiti ad un intero gruppo di pazienti."

Rationale. In general terms, research data should be 'FAIR', that is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation-solution [H2020], [HE].

Making data FINDABLE, including provisions for metadata

Aspects to be considered

Data discoverability, identifiability and locatability by the use of standard metadata and identification mechanism (e.g., persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers); naming conventions; search keywords; version numbers; provision of rich metadata for indexing.

Guidance

The Research Data Alliance provides a [Directory of Metadata Standards](#) that can be searched for discipline-specific standards and associated tools.

Mandatory Elements

The indication that a set of relevant metadata regarding each study of the I FAIR Program is collected and made findable according to the FAIR principles in the Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia.

Making data ACCESSIBLE

Aspects to be considered:

Data availability and openness; metadata availability even if the data is no longer accessible; accessibility restrictions (legal/contractual or voluntary); publication methods (e.g., deposition in a trusted repository) and timing in case of an embargo is applied; methods or software tools needed to access the data (software documentation, open source code, standardized access protocol); data, metadata, code and documentation deposition (e.g., open access repositories); data access committee; access conditions (e.g., machine-readable license); access control.

Guidance:

“Accessible data” doesn’t imply “open data”, the approach should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”⁷. The [Registry of Research Data Repositories](#) provides a useful listing of repositories that you can search to find a place of deposit.

Mandatory Elements

The indication that a set of relevant metadata regarding each study of the I FAIR Program is collected and made accessible according to the FAIR principles in the Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia.

⁷ Landi, A., Thompson, M., et al., The “A” of FAIR – As Open as Possible, as Closed as Necessary. *Data Intelligence* 2020; 2 (1-2): 47–55. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00027

Making data INTEROPERABLE

Aspects to be considered

Data interoperability for exchange and re-use (adherence to relevant standards for formats in compliance with available (open) software applications); data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies used; provision of ontological mappings to more commonly used ontologies in case of generating project specific ontologies or vocabularies; qualified references included in the data (e.g., cross links to other dataset from previous research).

Mandatory Elements

The indication that a set of relevant metadata regarding each study of the I FAIR Program is collected and made interoperable according to the FAIR principles in the Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia.

Increase data RE-USE (through clarifying licences)

Aspects to be considered

Data licenses for re-use by third parties; timing (e.g., data publication, embargo, duration of availability for re-use etc.); existent restrictions on data re-use; documentation to validate data analysis (e.g., codebooks, variable definitions, data cleaning procedures); provenance documentation with appropriate standards; data quality assurance processes; management of research outputs other than data (e.g., software, protocols, new materials, samples, etc.).

Guidance:

The [EUDAT B2SHARE](#) tool includes a built-in license wizard that facilitates the selection of an adequate license for research data.

Mandatory Elements

The indication that a set of relevant metadata regarding each study of the I FAIR Program is collected and made reusable according to the FAIR principles in the Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia.

3. Resources

Rationale: Explain the allocation of resources in terms of money, hardware, personnel and time that will be dedicated to data management/stewardship activities (e.g., data curation, production of metadata, archiving, etc.) and how it is planned to cover the costs. Responsibilities and duties of the involved staff should be defined as well (e.g., role, position, institution of the Principal Investigator - PI and the Data Steward - DS). **[H2020], [HE], [UniBi], [NWO], [HRB].**

Aspects to be considered

Budget, costs and staff time for the main activities during/after the project duration (data FAIRification, metadata collection/creation, data management, data acquisition/capture, data

quality/sharing/storage, back-up, etc.); resources for long term preservation (e.g., storage costs, staff time, etc.); roles and responsibilities (e.g., data management, DMP curator, PI, DS, personnel involved in the data collection/creation/acquisition, data ownership, responsible for sensitive/confidential data, other institutions or services involved and coordinator); additional specialist expertise or training; additional hardware or software. [H2020], [HE], [SNSF], [DCC], [UniBi], [SRC], [DCC], [NWO].

Mandatory Elements

Roles and responsibilities (e.g., data management, DMP curator, PI, DS, personnel involved in the data collection/creation/acquisition, data ownership, responsible for sensitive/confidential data, other institutions or services involved and coordinator).

4. Security, storage and backup

Rationale. Data backup, recovery and security measures are of an utmost importance, especially when working with personal or other sensitive data. This section should outline which measures are adopted, how they are put into practice, eventual standards or regulations considered (e.g., ISO 27001-Information security management) and the main procedures or facilities for storage, processing or transfer of personal or other sensitive data. [NWO], [SNSF], [H2020], [HE].

Aspects to be considered

Data and metadata security provisions (e.g., data recovery, automatic data backup, data access rights, technological solutions, responsible staff, etc.); storage and retention (e.g., certified repository, institutional/third parties storage, online/offline storage, locations, multiple copies, formats, etc.); security standards and legislation (e.g., regulations, confidentiality agreement, etc.); security risk analysis (e.g., main concerns, estimation, how they can be managed, etc.); personal and sensitive data protection measures (e.g., secure storage, transfer, anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, etc.); informed consent [H2020], [HE], [SNSF], [DCC], [SRC], [UniBi], [HRB], [NWO].

Guidance

Consider how data minimisation, pseudonymisation or anonymisation will affect data quality [HRB].

Mandatory Elements

Data and metadata security provisions (e.g., data recovery, automatic data backup, data access rights, technological solutions, responsible staff, etc.); storage and retention (e.g., certified repository, institutional/third parties storage, online/offline storage, locations, multiple copies, formats, etc.); security standards and legislation (e.g., regulations, confidentiality agreement, etc.); personal and sensitive data protection measures (e.g., secure storage, transfer, anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, etc.).

5. Ethical, legal, administrative and privacy aspects

Rationale. Ethical issues in research projects require specific measures in addition to ordinary data management procedures, such as data anonymization, ethics committees' approval, formal consent agreements, etc. In this section, all the relevant ethical issues in the project and their respective countermeasure should be outlined. Note that some of the content listed here may overlap with what is defined in the previous section. If additional legal or administrative issues are identified, such as Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) and ownership, they should be treated here as well [SNSF], [HRB].

Aspects to be considered

Security provisions for sensitive/personal data (data protection, recovery, secure storage and transfer); permissions for data handling (collection, processing, storing, etc.); relevant legislation and standards (e.g., GDPR); confidentiality agreement; informed consent (formal agreement, gaining, etc.); ethical issues; ethical review (IRB, Ethic Committee, protocols, approval dates, etc.); specific risks/measures for data security; support staff; data anonymization/pseudonymization and encryption; code of conduct; any national/institutional ethical guidelines followed; copyright and intellectual property of research data/artefacts (e.g. software, hardware); patent laws; licenses (e.g., CC-BY, CC-BY-NC, etc.); third-party research data or software in use (copyright, patent law or other intellectual property rights owner, restrictions, etc.); control access to data for multi-partner projects [H2020], [HE], [SNSF], [DCC], [NSF], [UniBi], [SRC], [HRB], [NWO].

Mandatory Elements

Security provisions for sensitive/personal data (data protection, recovery, secure storage and transfer); permissions for data handling (collection, processing, storing, etc.); relevant legislation and standards (e.g., GDPR); confidentiality agreement; informed consent (formal agreement, gaining, etc.); ethical issues; ethical review (IRB, Ethic Committee, protocols, approval dates, etc.); data anonymization/pseudonymization and encryption; code of conduct; any national/institutional ethical guidelines followed; copyright and intellectual property of research data/artefacts (e.g. software, hardware); patent laws; licenses (e.g., CC-BY, CC-BY-NC, etc.); third-party research data or software in use (copyright, patent law or other intellectual property rights owner, restrictions, etc.); control access to data for multi-partner projects.

Remember to indicate that the study protocol and the models of informed consents approved by the Institutional Ethical Review Board, when available, are stored in the Regional Registry of the Biomedical Research in Sardinia.

References

- **[UniBi]** Data Management Plans (DMP) - University of Bielefeld. Available at: <https://www.ub.uni-bielefeld.de/ub/digital/forschungsdaten/beratung/dmp/>
- **[SRC]** Swedish Research Council DMP Template. Available at: https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1424594839.pdf
- **[HRB]** Health Research Board (HRB) Ireland DMP Template. Available at: https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1814665590.pdf
- **[NWO]** Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO) Data Management Plan. Available at: https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1753695087.pdf
- **[NSF]** National Science Foundation (USA): NSF DMP Template. Available at: https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1794527806.pdf
- **[DCC]** Digital Curation Centre (DCC) DMP Template. Available at: https://dmptool.org/template_export/1936.pdf
- **[H2020]** European Commission (Horizon 2020): Initial DMP. Available at: https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1612436782.pdf
- **[HE]** European Commission : Horizon Europe Template. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx
- **[SNSF]** Data Management Plan – content of the mySNF form - Swiss National Science Foundation. Available at: http://www.snf.ch/SiteCollectionDocuments/DMP_content_mySNF-form_en.pdf